

Supplementary Material

Paleoseismicity of the western Humps fault on the Emu Plain, North Canterbury, New Zealand

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Supplementary material contains preferred (Figure S1 and Table S1) and alternate (Figure S2 and Table S2) OxCal age models for the timing of paleoearthquakes and stratigraphy in the McLean-1 trench.